

Participatory Rural Appraisal: A Creativity Improvement to Create Online Marketing Media

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ABSTRACT : This Participatory Rural Appraisal aims to empower Asy Syifa Business Group in marketing food products. Participants of this research are women who are members of the business group aged 40-55 years. The 50% of participants graduated from senior high schools as their educational background; the rest have bachelor and diploma degrees. Data collection methods used Focus Group Discussion and semi-structured interviews. Data analysis utilized qualitative descriptive analysis. PRA activities were carried out in four stages: 1) Conducting social mapping, 2) Creating flow analysis, 3) Conducting a SWOT analysis, 4) Designing an improvement program. PRA implementation in empowering Asy Syifa Business group can improve creativity create and maintain online marketing media.

KEYWORDS - Participatory Rural Appraisal, Creativity, Media, Marketing

I. INTRODUCTION

Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) are a means for community empowerment, both urban and rural societies. Therefore, the development of MSMEs is currently considered crucial for improving the people's economy. With the development of the people's economy, it can increase people's income, open job opportunities, and enhance the community's welfare.

Asy Syifa Group is a joint business unit operating a food sales business. This group employs about ten female members who produce cooked rice, side dishes, and various traditional foods. The business management is carried out using a traditional model, not the online one. Even though the media has a fixative ability which can reproduce an object more clearly in the form of an image, film, or audio conveyed to the user. The media also has an advantage of having a manipulative ability, which is to display objects or changes (manipulation) according to goals or needs [1].

In the marketing activities, this group has not utilized the media in the form of information technology applications. Its marketing media need to be adequately designed to provide information for consumers about product characteristics and how the product ordering process works [2].

Before the pandemic period, due to the covid-19 virus, this business was marketed through home stalls. However, due to this pandemic, this group experienced a decrease in turnover because the product marketing through home-based shops was no longer possible. One indicator of the business success is the total coverage area of product marketing so that the opportunity to get more significant profits and demand for products will also increase [3].

For this reason, the business operators need to increase the intensity and to improve creativity of marketing their products. Problems in marketing can be overcome using online media which is currently and widely used by the public, for example, social networking media, such as WhatsApp, Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram. The advantage of online marketing is that the media can provide visual, personality, and product identification information to have an emotional impact on consumers [4]. Online marketing can cut promotion costs by 80% and can create a comprehensive and fast marketing network. The networking also makes it easy for anyone to build a business networking without spending a lot of capital [5]. But not all business operators have skills in marketing products through online media.

According to McQuail [6], the advantages of online media marketing, namely: 1) interactive, because producers and consumers can interact even though they do not have to meet in person; 2) Social Presence, which

means that social media can build social relationships between producers and consumers; 3) Media richness, meaning that media wealth in bridging the needs of producers and potential consumers; 4) Autonomy, which provides the opportunity for users to manage content and manage media for promotion; 5) Personalization, which emphasizes that the message content in communication can be unique according to the characteristics of the producer.

The business group of *Asy Syifa* catering is currently trying to offer its products through WhatsApp groups. But the marketing strategy has not used attractive media and done by each member with different marketing models. This makes it challenging to monitor how much product marketing has been done.

As a result, this marketing model does not attract the consumers' attention. To introduce these products, the group need an innovative promotional media. Therefore, to improve creativity in marketing media, it is necessary to have a results-oriented community empowerment program, namely the Participatory Rural Appraisal (PRA) approach. PRA is an action research method developed to increase community participation in development. PRA enables communities to express and analyse their situation and plan and implement reforms within their group [7]. Therefore this approach has the advantage of allowing the group to carry out problem-solving activities independently.

II. RESEARCH METHODS

This research uses the Participatory Rural Appraisal approach because it can develop community knowledge and encourage people to participate in community empowerment programs actively. The steps taken were: 1) conducting social mapping, 2) making flow analysis, 3) conducting a SWOT analysis, 4) designing a repair program.

The participants are members of *Asy Syifa* Business Group, Purwokerto Indonesia. They were between 44-55 years old, and all of them were female. The 50% of the participants have a high school education; the rest have a bachelor and diploma education.

Data collection methods used Focus Group Discussion and semi-structured interviews. FGD was used to map the problems experienced by the group members. Meanwhile, semi-structured interviews were conducted to explore the potential, obstacles, challenges, and opportunities of the group members in empowering themselves. Qualitative descriptive analysis was used to analyse the results of the FGD and interviews.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Results of social mapping

Social mapping can provide a social image of *Asy Syifa's* business group, which includes members who play a role in social relations, social networks, the strengths and interests of each member in the group activities. The results of social mapping can be seen in table 1 below:

Table 1. Social Description of *Asy Syifa's* Business Group

Member's name	Age (Years)	Level of education	The catering business period (years)
A	44	3-year diploma	13
B	43	Bachelor	10
C	56	3-year diploma	8
D	40	Vocational high School	9
E	50	Bachelor	14
F	52	Senior High School	10
G	49	Vocational high School	10
H	44	Senior High School	3

All members of the Business Group have strength in the form of independence in the culinary business. The type of food produced is cooked rice and its side dishes as well as various kinds of snacks. The problems in the field of marketing are: 1) the marketing is only local, around the residence of group members, 2) not all group members have the ability to make promotional media, 3) Only two group members utilized social media

to promote their food products, 4) The emergence of several MSMEs (the competitors) engaged in the culinary field and carried out promotions through social media, 5) during the pandemic period due to covid-19, the number of consumers experienced a decline.

The results of social mapping also show that the Business Group management has coordinated with members to improve product marketing communications. Collaboration was carried out with internal parties, namely mosque administrators in the group's location, but the cooperation has not been carried out with external parties to increase the business productivity.

2. Results of flow analysis

The results of the problem analysis of *Asy Syifa* business group are described as follows:

Figure 1. Results of flow analysis

3. SWOT analysis

SWOT stands for Strength, Weakness, Opportunity, and Threat. SWOT analysis is a method to assist in strategy formulation. The analysis aims to identify strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats in the organizational environment. SWOT analysis is an analysis system that serves as a support for decision making [8]. To find out the SWOT of the *Asy Syifa* Business Group, an analysis of internal and external factors was carried out. The results of the analysis are described below:

Table 2. SWOT Analysis Results

	SW	STRENGTHS <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Group members have independence in production - Online marketing costs tend to be cheaper - Types of food products vary - There is a good relationship between group members, thus making communication smooth. 	WEAKNESS <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Not all group members have mastered internet-based promotion - Group members use personal selling - Do not have an excellent online marketing plan - Creativity in marketing is still low
OT	OPPORTUNITY <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The pattern of consumer behavior changes, from conventional information to internet-based information - Information technology is increasingly developing in all business sectors - Many social media are used as a means of marketing 	S-O Strategies : <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Expanding the distribution network for internet-based product marketing - Utilizing social media as a marketing tool 	W-O Strategies : <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Create social media accounts for product marketing - Provide training to create online marketing media - Providing a brand or name label on each food product
	TREAT <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - More and more catering businesses are using online marketing - Requires routine management of information on social media 	S-T Strategies : <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Build a network of cooperation with other parties - Making product offers online 	W-T Strategies : <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Providing training on food product marketing strategies - Designing a marketing program systematically

4. The Design of Improvement Program

To solve the identified problems, an empowerment program was carried out for the business group. In this activity, the methods used were a) community education, which involves counselling aimed at increasing partners' understanding of online marketing strategies; b) Training, which contains demonstrations of creating online media content; c) Assistance, which is assisting to optimize Instagram as an online marketing medium.

Before the activity was carried out, a pre-test is implemented to measure the readiness of group members in this empowerment activity. The results are as follows:

- a. 15% of participants have not implemented online promotion/marketing, 85% of participants have applied online marketing
- b. 85% of participants did promotions through the WhatsApp group, 15% via Facebook.
- c. 29% of participants already have a logo and brand for their culinary products, 71% do not have one.
- d. Only 29% of participants understand the elements presented in an online promotion, namely product photos, cellphone numbers, and promotional words.

These results indicate that most group members are familiar with social media as a promotional medium, but the promotion are limited to WhatsApp and Facebook. Most of the participants did not understand the elements that must be displayed in promoting food products on social media. Content on social media is crucial because it would determine success in attracting consumers to visit social media accounts to make purchases [2].

After the empowerment activity is carried out, an evaluation is carried out. Indicators of the success of this activity can be seen in 1) understanding of marketing strategies, 2) skills in creating online marketing media content, 3) ability to manage Instagram as an online marketing medium. Examples of online marketing media products designed by group members are;

Figure 2. Marketing Media

The results of the evaluation of the ability to create media content for marketing on social media can be seen as follows:

1. Aspects of Language

From the eight promotional media products in the form of food logos, it can be seen that not all of product logo used promotional sentences. Two media do not use persuasive sentences but using images.

2. Design relevance

Each of this eight promotional media products used different themes. Because the product being marketed is in the form of food, the design was adjusted to the product, using images of bay leaves and pictures of chefs. There was one design that does not match the product being marketed but accentuates the color.

3. Communicative

All promotional media products were communicative, either through persuasive sentences or images. Furthermore, the media was uploaded to the Instagram account asysyifaa.catering@gmail.com.

The results of this group empowerment indicate an increase in the quality of marketing through online media. Online marketing uses internet resources to communicate ideas and products to influence consumers [9]. In this activity, the social media that is considered fit for online product promotion is Instagram because it is the

most appropriate media for advertising using images [2]. Marketing through social media is not just advertising a product, but the producers can interact directly with consumers and get feedback to improve service and production [9]. Therefore the development of this activity can change the traditional marketing concept to social media-based marketing.

However, the use of social media becomes less effective if the social media-marketing management is not optimal. The producers are lacklack of time in managing social media, less routine product updates, less communicative photos and descriptions [6]. In this program, it was also found that there was no special IT team (operator) who would manage Instagram-based promotion that had been created before. For this reason, mentoring activities are still being carried out, especially for the members of *Asy Syifa* Business Group who are young and technology literate.

IV. CONCLUSION

PRA implementation in empowering *Asy Syifa* Business group can improve creativity create and maintain online marketing media. For the further marketing improvement, the cooperation with external parties is still needed.

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